

Botulinum toxin in modern clinical and aesthetic medicine: history, applications, risks and future perspectives

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Abstract

Botulinum toxin, a potent neurotoxin produced by *Clostridium botulinum*, has widespread applications in both medical and aesthetic practices due to its ability to inhibit neuromuscular transmission. In clinical medicine, it is used to treat various conditions such as chronic migraines, spasticity, and hyperhidrosis. In aesthetic medicine, it is primarily employed for wrinkle reduction and facial rejuvenation, providing significant efficacy with minimal recovery time. Despite its established therapeutic benefits, improper administration of botulinum toxin can lead to serious adverse effects, including muscle weakness, respiratory compromise, and localised reactions. Therefore, it is essential to ensure precise dosing, skilled injection techniques, and appropriate patient selection to maximise therapeutic outcomes while minimising risks. As the use of botulinum toxin continues to expand in both medical and cosmetic settings, there is a critical need for enhanced safety protocols and stringent regulation to ensure its safe and effective application.

Keywords

Clostridium botulinum, neurotoxin, aesthetic medicine, medical application, botulism

Introduction

The Clostridiaceae family comprises a diverse group of anaerobic, spore-forming bacteria with significant ecological roles and the potential to cause severe diseases through the production of potent toxins. These bacteria are widely distributed in various environments, including soil, water, and the gastrointestinal tracts of humans and animals (Kuehne 2019). Pathogenic species within this family, such as *Clostridium botulinum* (botulism), *Clostridium tetani* (tetanus), *Clostridium perfringens* (gas gangrene), and *Clostridium difficile* (pseudomembranous colitis), exert their effects primarily through exotoxin production (Fig. 1).

These toxins can be neurotoxic, cytotoxic, or enterotoxic, leading to diverse clinical manifestations (Carter et al. 2014). The ability to form heat-resistant spores enables these bacteria to survive harsh environmental conditions, facilitating their persistence, transmission, and pathogenic potential (Kuehne et al. 2019).

Botulinum neurotoxin (BoNT), the most potent and specific neurotoxin known, is synthesised by the anaerobic bacterium *Clostridium botulinum*, with a human LD₅₀ (i.v.) of about 2 ng/kg. BoNT was initially recognised as the aetiological agent of botulism, a serious condition that causes paralysis and respiratory failure (Montecucco and Molgó 2005). Over the past thirty

Figure 1. *Clostridium botulinum*.

years, progress in understanding the toxin's biology and mechanisms of action, along with the development of safe and effective modes of administration, has made it possible to utilise BoNT for therapeutic purposes in many medical and aesthetic fields. This progress was largely attributed to the improved understanding of the molecular mechanism, optimisation of dosing strategies, and enhanced risk management practices.

This study discusses the evolution of BoNT research, therapeutic indications, dosage recommendations, and risks following administration. Additionally, analysis of the potential associated pathologies and complications will serve as a reference point for evaluating the impact of BoNT in modern medicine and aesthetics.

Materials and methods

For this review, data were gathered and analysed from prominent scientific databases such as PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate, offering up-to-date, peer-reviewed publications on the pharmacological properties of botulinum neurotoxin, its various applications in both medical and aesthetic fields, dosing guidelines, methods of administration, associated risks, and their management. The data from these sources were compiled to provide a thorough overview of the current indications and potential risks related to the use of botulinum toxin.

Historical overview of the discovery of botulinum toxin

The story of BoNT is remarkable, as it transforms an element of danger into an astonishing medical achievement. The first case of poisoning was noted in 1820, when the German doctor Justinus Kerner identified a toxin that

turned out to be the cause of severe food poisoning, which is now called botulism (Pellett 2012). He was the first to suggest that the substance could also have some beneficial medicinal properties. *Clostridium botulinum*, the bacterium believed to be responsible for the poisoning, was first isolated by Emile Van Ermengem in 1895 (King et al. 2015).

In the second half of the 20th century, the military took an interest in botulinum toxin. It was investigated during World War II as a potential biological weapon (Lebeda et al. 2018). The study of BoNT as a biological weapon during this time led to improvements in the methods for obtaining and purifying crystalline botulinum toxin type A (BoNT-A). In the 1950s, Dr Vernon Brooks discovered the important fact that BoNT can block the conduction of nerve impulses to muscles (Erbguth 2008).

Therapeutic uses of BoNT were initiated following the discovery of its effectiveness in treating muscle spasms. In 1978, a significant milestone in medical history was achieved with the treatment of strabismus using BoNT-A. In 1989, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved BoNT-A for the treatment of ocular disorders, including blepharospasm and strabismus, after Dr Alan Scott, an ophthalmologist, refined the toxin for injection in the early 1980s. By 2002, the FDA had approved its use in aesthetic medicine, thereby granting wide acceptance of BoNT and establishing it as the most successful FDA-approved treatment for facial wrinkles (Whitcup 2021).

Pharmacology of botulinum toxin

Seven types of BoNT have been distinguished – A, B, C, D, E, F, and G – which differ from one another in their molecular structure and mechanism of action (Whitcup 2021). Only types A and B are known to have wide applications in medicine and aesthetics; the use of other types is rare and less understood (Rosales 2006).

BoNT-A products include Botox® (onabotulinumtoxinA), Dysport® (abobotulinumtoxinA), Vistabel® (onabotulinumtoxinA), and Xeomin® (incobotulinumtoxinA). They are similar in mechanism of action but differ in their efficacy, spread, diffusion, and safety profiles, which may be relevant in clinical applications (Slawek 2010; Carruthers 2013).

BoNT inhibits neuromuscular transmission, which prevents the nervous system from functioning. When this multi-molecule complex is in equilibrium at physiological pH, it quickly dissociates to release the active neurotoxin, which is endocytosed by nerve terminals. Muscle paralysis is the main effect of blocking acetylcholine release in the peripheral nervous system; the duration of the effect is determined by how long the neurotoxic molecules remain in the nerve terminals (Dressler 2005). BoNT acts specifically on SNARE proteins inside the nerve terminal, which are the major proteins that mediate the exocytosis of neurotransmitters. Cleavage of certain neuronal proteins prevents synaptic vesicle fusion and thereby blocks acetylcholine release from motor neurons – SNAP-25, syntaxin, and VAMP/synaptobrevin. This blockade induces muscle weakness or paralysis.

Depending on how long it takes for the cleaved SNARE proteins to regenerate and allow for the restoration of acetylcholine release, the effects of BoNT often last three to six months. BoNT does not affect nerve function, only muscle activity, which is considered safe when administered correctly and at a reduced dose (Dressler et al. 2005; Bozzi et al. 2006).

Botulinum toxin in medical practice

Botulinum toxin is widely used in medical practice for the treatment of various diseases, as presented in Fig. 2.

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of cervical dystonia

Cervical dystonia is a neuromuscular condition that causes the affected neck musculature to contract involuntarily, inducing abnormal head posture and head movements that often involve pain and difficulties in performing daily tasks. The major treatment approaches include rehabilitation and medications, BoNT injections, and surgery on rare occasions, with BoNT undoubtedly the most favoured option. Muscles commonly injected include the splenius capitis, sternocleidomastoid, trapezius, and others (Brashear 2001).

The starting dose usually follows a common regimen, e.g., 500 IU Dysport®. Re-dosing depends on the clinical response to treatment. Total doses vary during the same session, with Dysport® averaging approximately 652.5 IU per session and Botox® around 159.5 IU, with Xeomin® doses equivalent to Botox doses (Comella and Thompson 2006).

Common side effects are generally mild and transient, including dysphagia, neck weakness, and discomfort. Therefore, treatment is individualised to provide maximal benefit to the patient while minimising side effects. Improvement in symptoms, with sustained benefits over time, indicates that BoNT injections have positive effects (Hauser et al. 2013).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of blepharospasm

Involuntary constriction of the eyelid muscles (the orbicularis oculi, corrugator, and procerus), resulting in chronic eyelid closure, is a focal dystonia-like condition called blepharospasm. BoNT-A has always been the first-line treatment for this condition. Injections of BoNT-A predominantly target the orbicularis oculi muscle, which is responsible for the closure of the eyelids. Doses vary between 15 and 42.5 IU per session. BoNT-A is highly effective in 86% of patients, who reported good to excellent results (Chauhan et al. 2013). Common side effects include weakness of the orbicularis oculi muscle, ptosis, dry eye, and ecchymosis, which are transient and generally mild (Jochim et al. 2020).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of spasticity after stroke

Post-stroke spasticity is characterised by an abnormal increase in muscle tone due to a pathology within the central nervous system. This condition interferes with voluntary movements, particularly those related to motor functions. BoNT is administered to reduce muscle tone in patients with chronic spasticity following neurological injury (Santamato et al. 2015).

BoNT-A provides a noticeable reduction in muscle tone and spasticity in both the upper and lower limbs following a stroke. It is regarded as safe, with adverse effects being rare and generally mild. The gastrocnemius is the most commonly treated muscle for lower limb spasticity, while several flexor muscles are typically targeted for upper limb spasticity (Santamato et al. 2015).

The choice of specific muscles and dosage depends on the severity and location of the spasticity. Guidelines suggest a maximum of 600 IU of onabotulinumtoxinA/incobotulinumtoxinA or 1500 IU of abobotulinumtoxinA to minimise the risk of significant adverse events (Brashear et al. 2002).

Figure 2. Application of botulinum toxin in medical practice.

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of chronic migraine

Chronic migraine headaches are effectively managed with BoNT-A. Recent studies demonstrate a reduction in migraine frequency ranging from 0.23 to 1.56 fewer headaches per month (Grazzi and Usai 2015; Bruloy et al. 2019). The PREEMPT protocol, which is the most widely utilised treatment regimen, involves the administration of 155 IU of onabotulinumtoxinA (Botox®) (Begasse de Dhaem et al. 2020). Injections are directed at the *frontalis*, *corrugator supercilii*, *procerus*, *temporalis*, *occipitalis*, and *orbicularis oculi* muscles. The “follow the pain” approach is frequently employed, targeting the muscles where the pain is most intense (Naprienko and Smekalkina 2015).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of hyperhidrosis

Hyperhidrosis is characterised by excessive sweating due to the overactivity of sweat glands. BoNT-A effectively manages hyperhidrosis by inhibiting acetylcholine release, thereby reducing sweat production, particularly in the axillary, palmar, and plantar regions (Doft et al. 2012). OnabotulinumtoxinA and incobotulinumtoxinA are commonly used, typically administered at doses of approximately 100 IU per side, with effects lasting between 6 and 10 months (Rossel et al. 2013). The use of BoNT-A for treatment is considered safe. Muscle weakness, especially in the hands, may occur but generally resolves within a few weeks (Campanati et al. 2014).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases

BoNT reduces muscle activity by affecting neuromuscular transmission, and its increasing use has proven effective in treating various gastrointestinal (GI) disorders. The most relevant GI diseases treated with BoNT include:

Achalasia: BoNT injections at the lower oesophageal sphincter help alleviate pressure, improving oesophageal emptying and providing symptomatic relief, especially in patients who are unsuitable for surgery or pneumatic dilation. Typically, 100 IU of BoNT is injected into the lower oesophageal sphincter (Yamaguchi et al. 2015).

Gastroparesis: Delayed gastric emptying is managed by injecting BoNT into the pylorus, reducing pyloric pressure and enabling gastric emptying. This provides symptom relief in cases where other treatments may be ineffective. Doses of BoNT-A range from 80 to 200 IU (DeSantis and Huang 2007).

Hypertonic gastrointestinal disorders: Certain spastic conditions, such as sphincter of Oddi dysfunction or hypertensive oesophageal disorders, can be treated with BoNT injections to relax muscle hypertonia and provide symptom relief by inhibiting acetylcholine release. The exact dosing for these conditions remains less defined, but BoNT is typically used to relax the targeted sphincter and relieve symptoms (Bromer et al. 2005; Vittal and Pasricha 2006).

BoNT has an excellent safety profile, with a low incidence of side effects, making it a valuable option for high-risk patients who are not candidates for invasive procedures. Studies show that about 43% of patients respond to treatment, with a median duration of symptom relief lasting approximately five months (Chen 2012).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of urinary incontinence

Urinary incontinence refers to the involuntary loss of bladder control, often due to dysfunction in the detrusor muscle, the sphincter, or the nerve pathways that regulate urination. OnabotulinumtoxinA is used to treat urinary incontinence resulting from neurogenic detrusor overactivity (NDO) and overactive bladder (OAB).

In NDO, a typical dose of 200 IU is injected into the detrusor muscle, showing efficacy in reducing incontinence and improving urodynamic outcomes in patients with multiple sclerosis and spinal cord injuries (da Silva et al. 2015). For OAB, 100 IU is injected into the detrusor muscle to decrease incontinence, reduce urinary frequency, and enhance the patient’s quality of life (da Silva 2015; Yokoyama et al. 2020).

The injections are administered directly into the bladder, avoiding the trigone area to minimise potential side effects. Despite its strong efficacy, common side effects include urinary tract infections, urinary retention (sometimes requiring catheterisation), and transient muscle weakness or fatigue (Yokoyama et al. 2020).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of myofascial pain syndrome

Although the use of BoNT in treating myofascial pain syndrome remains controversial, some studies provide strong evidence of significant pain relief and enhanced quality of life, while others report no clear benefit over placebo (Cheshire et al. 1994). The dosage of BoNT varies widely across studies, ranging from low doses (5 IU) to high doses (up to 400 IU), which contributes to variability in the results (Göbel et al. 2006; Ojala et al. 2006). Most side effects are mild to moderate and temporary, and BoNT is generally well tolerated. A common adverse effect is muscle weakness (Göbel 2006).

Botulinum toxin in aesthetic medicine

The therapeutic index for BoNT is considered to be very high, with approximately 30 IU typically used in aesthetic procedures, while the estimated lethal dose (LD₅₀) is around 3000 IU (Bigalke 2013).

BoNT is widely used in aesthetics for the treatment of facial wrinkles, with dosages adjusted based on specific indications and individual patient characteristics (Small 2014) (Fig. 3). Higher doses are often needed for men, as they tend to have larger muscle mass (Baumann et al. 2009).

Figure 3. Main indications of botulinum toxin in aesthetic medicine.

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of glabellar lines

BoNT is a standard treatment for glabellar lines, primarily targeting the *corrugator supercilii* and *procerus* muscles. Botox®/Vistabel® and Dysport® typically require 50 IU, administered across five injection sites arranged in a swallow-like pattern (Dorizas et al. 2014). Due to their larger muscle mass, men generally require higher doses, with 40 IU considered the minimum starting dose (Monheit et al. 2007).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of forehead wrinkles

BoNT injections are commonly used to treat the *frontalis* and glabellar muscles, reducing the appearance of forehead wrinkles. Accurate placement of the toxin in the *frontalis* muscle is crucial to minimise complications such as ptosis. Intramuscular injections are effective but may carry a higher risk of such complications. Intradermal injections reduce this risk but may cause more discomfort during the injection process (Mitra et al. 2024).

Dosage should be tailored to each patient, taking into account muscle mass, anatomical factors, and treatment goals, with particular attention to populations with smaller muscle mass, such as Asians (Hong 2023). For forehead wrinkles, BoNT-A dosing typically involves nine injections, arranged in two rows, with 1 IU per injection site (Yi et al. 2024).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of crow's feet wrinkles

Crow's feet wrinkles are among the most effectively treated by BoNT, which temporarily paralyses the *orbicularis oculi* muscle. A typical dose for crow's feet is approximately 12 IU per side, with injections targeting the lateral aspect of the muscle (Small 2014). Recently, a novel injection technique using ultrasound guidance has been

shown to enhance both the precision and efficacy of the treatment (Popescu et al. 2024).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of marionette lines

BoNT-A is widely used for the reduction of marionette lines, which are the lines running from the corners of the mouth down to the chin. In a study involving 189 patients, the average dose for treatment was 113.8 IU, with doses ranging from 50 to 180 IU (D'Emilio and Rosati 2020). The treatment is generally well tolerated, with mild complications. Recommendations for treating marionette lines with onabotulinumtoxinA include careful evaluation of the patient's facial anatomy and muscle activity (Bertossi et al. 2018). Dosing should be individualised based on the severity of the wrinkles and the desired outcome. Combining BoNT-A with other treatments, such as hyaluronic acid fillers, may improve the aesthetic result of marionette lines. This combination can provide a more balanced and natural appearance by addressing both muscle activity and volume loss (Borodic 2013).

Botulinum toxin for eyebrow lift and reduction of gummy smile

BoNT is widely used in aesthetic medicine for eyebrow elevation and correction of gummy smiles. For eyebrow lifting, BoNT is injected into the glabellar region to relax the muscles that pull the brow downward, allowing for a gentle upward movement. The dosage typically ranges from 10 to 40 IU, with injections placed across the glabellar area, extending from the midline to the mid-pupillary line (Carruthers and Carruthers 2007). For a gummy smile, BoNT is injected into the *levator labii superioris* muscle to prevent excessive gum display when smiling. Typically, 2 IU are administered at each injection site, with 2–4 sites targeted (Costa et al. 2022).

Botulinum toxin for the treatment of platysmal band

BoNT is commonly used to reduce the appearance of platysmal bands, the vertical lines that develop with age on the neck. The treatment works by relaxing the *platysma* muscle, which softens the lines and improves the neck's appearance. Typically, 20 to 50 IU are used, with 2 to 4 IU injected at each site, depending on the thickness of the bands and individual patient anatomy. Injections are administered along the muscle from the angle of the mandible to the clavicle (Obagi and Golubets 2017; Sugrue et al. 2019).

Special requirements after botulinum toxin administration

Regardless of the injection site or treatment purpose, BoNT should always be diluted with 0.9% saline to ensure accurate concentration. It is typically diluted to 50 IU per 1 cc, with a maximum recommended dose of 400 IU per session (Rzany et al. 2013).

For optimal safety and efficacy, reconstituted BoNT should be used within a specified timeframe. Research indicates that, under aseptic conditions, it remains sterile at room temperature for up to four hours. BoNT injections should only be performed by trained and qualified healthcare professionals with expertise in injection techniques (Brisinda et al. 2007).

In the European Union, the administration of botulinum toxin is subject to stringent regulations, permitting its use exclusively by qualified healthcare practitioners. This encompasses physicians with specialised training in pertinent disciplines, including dermatology, neurology, or plastic surgery, who have completed the necessary education and certification for the application of BoNT (Hubble et al. 2013).

To ensure optimal treatment outcomes after BoNT injections, it is important to avoid massaging, rubbing, or touching the treated areas, as these actions can cause unintended diffusion of the toxin (Evin et al. 2024). Patients should refrain from strenuous activity for at least four hours and avoid lying flat immediately after the procedure. Exposure to heat, such as from saunas or hot baths, should be limited for 48 hours (Gupta et al. 2024). Additionally, alcohol consumption and the use of anticoagulants on the day of the injection are discouraged, as they can increase the risk of bruising and other complications. Patients should be mindful of potential adverse effects, such as pain, swelling, or ptosis, and contact their healthcare provider if these occur. Regular follow-up appointments are recommended to monitor progress and ensure the best possible results (Hu et al. 2023).

Clinical manifestations of botulinum toxin intoxication

BoNT intoxication can cause local and systemic symptoms depending on the dose, site of administration, and spread of

the toxin. Symptoms appear gradually and sometimes begin 12–36 hours after toxin administration, which can progress to life-threatening conditions (Adler and Franz 2016; Szuch et al. 2017; Floresta et al. 2020). Local adverse reactions include ptosis of the eyelid, asymmetry of the face, dysphagia with injections in the neck, and local muscle weakness or paresis near the injection site. Manifestations of systemic effects (with overdose or spread of the toxin) are generalised muscle weakness, dyspnoea, diplopia, dysphonia, xerostomia, mydriasis, and disarticulation.

Diagnosis and differential diagnosis of botulism

Diagnosis is mainly clinical, with a recent history of exposure to BoNT or ingestion of contaminated food. Common manifestations include blurred vision, double vision, dry mouth, constipation, and symmetric paresis of the cranial nerves followed by flaccid paralysis (Proverbio et al. 2016).

Electromyography is particularly useful in severe cases. It typically reveals characteristic findings such as decreased compound muscle action potentials with low amplitudes, shortened motor unit potential duration, and mild waning of repetitive low-frequency stimulations. These findings can assist in diagnosing the condition and help guide the appropriate administration of botulinum antitoxin (Rao et al. 2021).

Differential diagnosis

Several conditions share clinical features with botulism and should be considered during diagnosis:

- **Myasthenia gravis:** Both conditions cause muscle weakness, but in myasthenia gravis the weakness is variable, worsens with activity, and improves with rest. It can be diagnosed through antibody testing and a positive response to acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (Juel and Massey 2007).
- **Guillain-Barré Syndrome:** This condition presents with symmetric muscle weakness that progresses in an ascending pattern, often following an infection. Diagnosis is confirmed by electrophysiological testing and cerebrospinal fluid analysis (Donaghy 2006).
- **Tetanus:** Tetanus is characterised by muscle stiffness and spasms, particularly in the jaw. It is distinguished by muscle spasticity and a history of a contaminated wound (Restani et al. 2012).
- **Stroke:** Stroke presents with sudden-onset focal neurological deficits and muscle weakness, which can be confirmed through neuroimaging. In contrast to botulism, which has a more gradual onset and symmetric descending paralysis, stroke typically involves sudden, localised neurological impairment (Lonati et al. 2020).

Management of botulinum toxin intoxication

Once BoNT binds to nerve endings, there is no specific antidote to neutralise its effects. Therefore, botulinum intoxication requires urgent medical attention, as complications such as respiratory failure may arise. Without treatment, the mortality rate for botulism can be as high as 65%. However, with modern interventions—including administration of botulinum antitoxin and intensive supportive care—this has been reduced to 15–25% (Machamer et al. 2022).

Treatment strategies depend on symptom severity and include both supportive measures and specific interventions. Initial steps involve clinical examination and laboratory confirmation. Immediate administration of botulinum antitoxin to neutralise unbound toxin, along with respiratory support (such as mechanical ventilation if required), should follow. The patient's condition and possible complications—including neurological and respiratory issues—must be closely monitored. Once stabilised, rehabilitation and physiotherapy are initiated to restore muscle strength. Despite advances in treatment, prognosis largely depends on the speed of intervention and the severity of the poisoning (Winner et al. 2020).

Future perspectives and further research on the applications of botulinum toxin

BoNT has a broad range of current medical applications and shows promise in several emerging fields. In urology, it may be used to treat prostate conditions, from benign prostatic hyperplasia to chronic nonbacterial prostatitis, although further research is needed to confirm its efficacy (Chuang and Chancellor 2006). In gynaecology, ongoing studies are exploring its potential in the treatment of chronic pelvic pain and vaginismus, though optimal dosages and injection sites remain undetermined (Etrusco et al. 2023). In otolaryngology, BoNT is applied in managing spasmodic dysphonia, vocal tremor, chronic salivary gland disorders, and chronic rhinitis, with emerging applications for tinnitus and synkinesis (Pickett and Rosales 2011).

BoNT is also widely used in cosmetic and dermatological procedures. Newer formulations such as daxibotulinumtoxinA offer longer durations of action, while BoNT-E provides a more rapid onset but with a shorter duration. Off-label uses—including treatment of androgenic alopecia and oily skin—are becoming more frequent, and ongoing research may support future regulatory approvals (Phan et al. 2021).

Further studies are required to better understand BoNT's mechanisms of action across tissues and conditions, enabling more targeted and individualised treatments. Long-term investigations are also essential to evaluate the potential for antibody formation and its impact on treatment efficacy.

From a safety standpoint, formulations should be rigorously monitored, and injection techniques continually refined to minimise adverse effects. Regulatory approval will be critical for expanding therapeutic indications. Additionally, BoNT should be further explored in neurological disorders, especially in combination therapies to enhance clinical outcomes.

Conclusion

BoNT has a wide range of applications in both medical and aesthetic fields when administered according to established indications and clinical guidelines. Ongoing research and recent discoveries suggest a promising future for BoNT, with significant potential to expand its therapeutic scope. Despite its potent neurotoxicity and associated risks, the past three decades have seen a marked increase in its clinical use. While the benefits are considerable, BoNT must be applied with thorough medical knowledge, individualised assessment, and precise dosing to minimise risks and prevent undesirable side effects.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Adler M, Franz DR (2016) The Toxicology of Airborne Pathogens and Toxins. In: Salem H, Katz SA (Eds) *The Toxicology of Airborne Pathogens and Toxins*. The Royal Society of Chemistry, 167–185.
- Baumann L, Brandt FS, Kane MA, Donofrio LM (2009) An analysis of efficacy data from four phase III studies of botulinum neurotoxin type A-ABO for the treatment of glabellar lines. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal* 29(6 Suppl): S57–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asj.2009.09.012>
- Begasse de Dhaem O, Gharedaghi MH, Rizzoli P (2020) Modifications to the PREEMPT Protocol for OnabotulinumtoxinA Injections for Chronic Migraine in Clinical Practice. *Headache* 60(7): 1365–1375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/head.13823>
- Bertossi D, Cavallini M, Cirillo P, Fundarò SP, Quartucci S, Sciuto C, Tonini D, Trocchi G, Signorini M (2018) Italian consensus report on the aesthetic use of onabotulinum toxin A. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 17(5): 719–730. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.12729>
- Bigalke H (2013) Botulinum toxin: application, safety, and limitations. *Current Topics in Microbiology and Immunology* 364: 307–317. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-33570-9_14
- Borodic GE (2013) Use of fillers as adjunct therapy for the treatment of lower face hemifacial spasm. *Ophthalmic Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery* 29(3): 225–226. <https://doi.org/10.1097/IOP.0b013e318289577e>
- Bozzi Y, Costantin L, Antonucci F, Caleo M (2006) Action of botulinum neurotoxins in the central nervous system: antiepileptic effects. *Neurotoxicity Research* 9(2–3): 197–203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03033939>
- Brashear A, Gordon MF, Elovic E, Kassicieh VD, Marciniak C, Do M, Lee CH, Jenkins S, Turkel C; Botox Post-Stroke Spasticity Study Group (2002) Intramuscular injection of botulinum toxin for the treatment of wrist and finger spasticity after a stroke. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 347(6): 395–400. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa011892>
- Brashear A (2001) The botulinum toxins in the treatment of cervical dystonia. *Seminars in Neurology* 21(1): 85–90. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2001-13123>
- Brisinda G, Cadeddu F, Mazzeo P, Maria G (2007) Botulinum toxin A for the treatment of chronic anal fissure. *Expert Review of Gastroenterology & Hepatology* 1(2): 219–228. <https://doi.org/10.1586/17474124.1.2.219>
- Bromer MQ, FriedenberG F, Miller LS, Fisher RS, Swartz K, Parkman HP (2005) Endoscopic pyloric injection of botulinum toxin A for the treatment of refractory gastroparesis. *Gastrointestinal Endoscopy* 61(7): 833–839. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0016-5107\(05\)00328-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0016-5107(05)00328-7)
- Bruloy E, Sinna R, Grolleau JL, Bout-Roumzeilles A, Berard E, Chaput B (2019) Botulinum Toxin versus Placebo: A Meta-Analysis of Prophylactic Treatment for Migraine. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery* 143(1): 239–250. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.00000000000005111>
- Campanati A, Giuliadori K, Martina E, Giuliano A, Ganzetti G, Offidani A (2014) Onabotulinumtoxin type A (Botox®) versus Incobotulinumtoxin type A (Xeomin®) in the treatment of focal idiopathic palmar hyperhidrosis: results of a comparative double-blind clinical trial. *Journal of Neural Transmission (Vienna)* 121(1): 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-013-1074-1>
- Carruthers A, Carruthers J (2007) Eyebrow height after botulinum toxin type A to the glabella. *Dermatologic Surgery* 33(1 Suppl): S26–S31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1524-4725.2006.32328.x>
- Carruthers J, Fournier N, Kerschner M, Ruiz-Avila J, Trindade de Almeida AR, Kaeuper G (2013) The convergence of medicine and neurotoxins: a focus on botulinum toxin type A and its application in aesthetic medicine--a global, evidence-based botulinum toxin consensus education initiative: part II. *Dermatologic Surgery* 39(3 Pt 2): 510–525. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dsu.12148>
- Carter GP, Cheung JK, Larcombe S, Lyras D (2014) Regulation of toxin production in the pathogenic clostridia. *Molecular Microbiology* 91(2): 221–231. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mmi.12469>
- Chauhan DS, Cariappa KM, Guruprasad Y (2013) Botulinum toxin type a for the treatment of hyperkinetic lines of the face. *Journal of Maxillofacial and Oral Surgery* 12(2): 173–183. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12663-012-0407-1>
- Chen S (2012) Clinical uses of botulinum neurotoxins: current indications, limitations and future developments. *Toxins (Basel)* 4(10): 913–939. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins4100913>
- Cheshire WP, Abashian SW, Mann DJ (1994) Botulinum toxin in the treatment of myofascial pain syndrome. *Pain* 59(1): 65–69. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3959\(94\)90048-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3959(94)90048-5)
- Chuang YC, Chancellor MB (2006) The application of botulinum toxin in the prostate. *The Journal of Urology* 176(6 Pt 1): 2375–2382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2006.07.127>
- Comella CL, Thompson PD (2006) Treatment of cervical dystonia with botulinum toxins. *European Journal of Neurology* 13(Suppl 1): 16–20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-1331.2006.01440.x>
- Costa AB, Romansina D, Ramalho J, Pereira P, Tedesco TK, Morimoto S, Gonçalves F, Ramalho KM (2022) Botulinum Toxin A in the Management of a Gummy Smile: A Clinical Controlled Preliminary Study. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal* 42(4): 421–430. <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjab342>
- da Silva CM, Chancellor MB, Smith CP, Cruz F (2015) Use of botulinum toxin for genitourinary conditions: What is the evidence? *Toxicology* 107(Pt A): 141–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxicon.2015.07.333>
- D'Emilio R, Rosati G (2020) Full-face treatment with onabotulinumtoxinA: Results from a single-center study. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology* 19(4): 809–816. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocd.13130>
- DeSantis ER, Huang S (2007) Botulinum toxin type A for treatment of refractory gastroparesis. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy* 64(21): 2237–2240. <https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp060394>
- Doft MA, Hardy KL, Ascherman JA (2012) Treatment of hyperhidrosis with botulinum toxin. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal* 32(2): 238–244. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1090820X11434506>
- Donaghy M (2006) Neurologists and the threat of bioterrorism. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 249(1): 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2006.06.004>
- Dorizas A, Krueger N, Sadick NS (2014) Aesthetic uses of the botulinum toxin. *Dermatologic Clinics* 32(1): 23–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.det.2013.09.009>
- Dressler D, Saberi FA, Barbosa ER (2005) Botulinum toxin: mechanisms of action. *Arquivos de Neuro-Psiquiatria* 63(1): 180–185. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0004-282x2005000100035>
- Erbguth FJ (2008) From poison to remedy: the chequered history of botulinum toxin. *Journal of Neural Transmission (Vienna)* 115(4): 559–565. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-007-0728-2>
- Etrusco A, Geru M, Laganà AS, Chiantera V, Giannini A, Buzzaccarini G (2023) Use of botulinum toxin in aesthetic medicine and

- gynaecology: current approaches, controversies, and future directions. *Przegląd Menopauzalny (Menopause Review)* 22(3): 155–160. <https://doi.org/10.5114/pm.2023.131457>
- Evin N, Sifil MK, Aghazada TM, Özcan ED, Guneren E (2024) Velopharyngeal Insufficiency After Botox Injection for Persistent Bruxism. *Journal of Craniofacial Surgery* 35(2): 495–497. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SCS.00000000000009769>
- Floresta G, Patamia V, Gentile D, Molteni F, Santamato A, Rescifina A, Vecchio M (2020) Repurposing of FDA-Approved Drugs for Treating Iatrogenic Botulism: A Paired 3D-QSAR/Docking Approach†. *ChemMedChem* 15(2): 256–262. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cmde.201900594>
- Göbel H, Heinze A, Reichel G, Heffer H, Benecke R; Dysport Myofascial Pain Study Group (2006) Efficacy and safety of a single botulinum type A toxin complex treatment (Dysport) for the relief of upper back myofascial pain syndrome. *Pain* 125(1–2): 82–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pain.2006.05.001>
- Grazzi L, Usai S (2015) Onabotulinum toxin A (Botox) for chronic migraine treatment: an Italian experience. *Neurological Sciences* 36(Suppl 1): 33–35. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10072-015-2140-2>
- Gupta AD, Baguley I, Estell J, Geffon S, Goh K, Rawicki B, de Graaf S, Olver J (2024) Statement of the Rehabilitation Medicine Society of Australia and New Zealand for the therapeutic use of botulinum toxin A in spasticity management. *Internal Medicine Journal* 54(1): 178–182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imj.16300>
- Hauser RA, Truong D, Hubble J, Coleman C, Beffy JL, Chang S, Picaud P (2013) AbobotulinumtoxinA (Dysport) dosing in cervical dystonia: an exploratory analysis of two large open-label extension studies. *Journal of Neural Transmission (Vienna)* 120(2): 299–307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-012-0872-1>
- Hong SO (2023) Cosmetic Treatment Using Botulinum Toxin in the Oral and Maxillofacial Area: A Narrative Review of Esthetic Techniques. *Toxins (Basel)* 15(2): 82. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins15020082>
- Hu X, Guo K, Li J, Wang X, Liu H, Yu Q, Kuang G, Li G, Huang J, Li H, Lin Z, Xiong N (2023) Postoperative ecchymoma of eyelid after botulinum toxin injection for hemifacial spasm: a case report. *Frontiers in Neurology* 14: 1171303. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2023.1171303>
- Hubble J, Schwab J, Hubert C, Abbott CC (2013) Dysport (botulinum toxin type A) in routine therapeutic usage: a telephone needs assessment survey of European physicians to evaluate current awareness and adherence to product labeling changes. *Clinical Neuropharmacology* 36(4): 122–127. <https://doi.org/10.1097/WNF.0b013e3182926e630>
- Jochim A, Meindl T, Huber C, Mantel T, Zwirner S, Castrop F, Haslinger B (2020) Treatment of blepharospasm and Meige's syndrome with abo- and onabotulinumtoxinA: long-term safety and efficacy in daily clinical practice. *Journal of Neurology* 267(1): 267–275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-019-09581-w>
- Juel VC, Massey JM (2007) Myasthenia gravis. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases* 2: 44. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1750-1172-2-44>
- King A, Quirouet A, Moore CK (2015) Urologic applications of botulinum toxin. *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine* 82(7): 456–464. <https://doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.82a.13166>
- Kuehne SA, Rood JJ, Lyras D (2019) Clostridial Genetics: Genetic Manipulation of the Pathogenic Clostridia. *Microbiology Spectrum* 7(3): 16. <https://doi.org/10.1128/microbiolspec.GPP3-0040-2018>
- Lebeda FJ, Adler M, Dembek ZF (2018) Yesterday and Today: The Impact of Research Conducted at Camp Detrick on Botulinum Toxin. *Military Medicine* 183(5–6): 85–95. <https://doi.org/10.1093/milmed/usx047>
- Lonati D, Schicchi A, Crevani M, Buscaglia E, Scaravaggi G, Maida F, Cirronis M, Petrolini VM, Locatelli CA (2020) Foodborne Botulism: Clinical Diagnosis and Medical Treatment. *Toxins (Basel)* 12(8): 509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins12080509>
- Machamer JB, Vazquez-Cintron EJ, O'Brien SW, Kelly KE, Altvater AC, Pagarigan KT, Dubee PB, Ondeck CA, McNutt PM (2022) Antidotal treatment of botulism in rats by continuous infusion with 3,4-diaminopyridine. *Molecular Medicine* 28(1): 61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s10020-022-00487-4>
- Mitra R, Raja VBKK, Panneerselvam E (2024) Comparison of Wrinkle Patterns Generated by Intradermal and Intramuscular Botulinum Toxin Injections by Clinical Evaluation. *Journal of Maxillofacial and Oral Surgery* 23(3): 670–675. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12663-024-02141-4>
- Monheit G, Carruthers A, Brandt F, Rand R (2007) A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study of botulinum toxin type A for the treatment of glabellar lines: determination of optimal dose. *Dermatologic Surgery* 33(1 Suppl): S51–59. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1524-4725.2006.32332.x>
- Montecucco C, Molgó J (2005) Botulinum neurotoxins: revival of an old killer. *Current Opinion in Pharmacology* 5(3): 274–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coph.2004.12.006>
- Naprienko MV, Smekalkina LV (2015) [Strategies on the improvement of chronic migraine treatment efficacy]. *Zhurnal Nevrologii i Psikhiiatrii imeni S.S. Korsakova* 115(12): 70–73. <https://doi.org/10.17116/jnevro201511511270-73> [in Russian]
- Obagi S, Golubets K (2017) Mild to Moderate Dysphagia Following Very Low-dose Abobotulinumtoxin A for Platysmal Bands. *Journal of Drugs in Dermatology* 16(9): 929–930.
- Ojala T, Arokoski JP, Partanen J (2006) The effect of small doses of botulinum toxin a on neck-shoulder myofascial pain syndrome: a double-blind, randomized, and controlled crossover trial. *The Clinical Journal of Pain* 22(1): 90–96. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ajp.0000151871.51406.c3>
- Pellet S (2012) Learning from the past: historical aspects of bacterial toxins as pharmaceuticals. *Current Opinion in Microbiology* 15(3): 292–299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2012.05.005>
- Phan K, Younessi S, Dubin D, Lin MJ, Khorasani H (2022) Emerging off-label esthetic uses of botulinum toxin in dermatology. *Dermatologic Therapy* 35(1): e15205. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.15205>
- Pickett A, Rosales RL (2011) New trends in the science of botulinum toxin-A as applied in dystonia. *International Journal of Neuroscience* 121(Suppl 1): 22–34. <https://doi.org/10.3109/00207454.2010.539306>
- Popescu MN, Beiu C, Iliescu CA, Racoviță A, Berteanu M, Iliescu MG, Stănescu AMA, Radaschin DS, Popa LG (2024) Ultrasound-Guided Botulinum Toxin-A Injections into the Masseter Muscle for Both Medical and Aesthetic Purposes. *Toxins (Basel)* 16(10): 413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins16100413>
- Proverbio MR, Lamba M, Rossi A, Siani P (2016) Early diagnosis and treatment in a child with foodborne botulism. *Anaerobe* 39: 189–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anaerobe.2015.12.002>
- Rao AK, Sobel J, Chatham-Stephens K, Luquez C (2021) Clinical Guidelines for Diagnosis and Treatment of Botulism, 2021. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report: Recommendations and Reports* 70(2): 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.r7002a1>
- Restani L, Giribaldi F, Manich M, Bercsenyi K, Menendez G, Rossetto O, Caleo M, Schiavo G (2012) Botulinum neurotoxins A and E undergo retrograde axonal transport in primary motor neurons. *PLOS Pathogens* 8(12): e1003087. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1003087>

- Rosales RL, Bigalke H, Dressler D (2006) Pharmacology of botulinum toxin: differences between type A preparations. *European Journal of Neurology* 13(Suppl 1): 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-1331.2006.01438.x>
- Rossel K, Hymnelius K, Swartling C (2013) Botulinum toxin type A and B improve quality of life in patients with axillary and palmar hyperhidrosis. *Acta Dermato-Venereologica* 93(3): 335–339. <https://doi.org/10.2340/00015555-1464>
- Rzany B, Fratila AA, Fischer TC, Hilton S, Pavicic T, Rothhaar A, Sattler G, Sommer B, Pickett A (2013) Recommendations for the best possible use of botulinum neurotoxin type a (Speywood units) for aesthetic applications. *Journal of Drugs in Dermatology* 12(1): 80–84.
- Santamato A, Micello MF, Ranieri M, Valeno G, Albano A, Baricich A, Cisari C, Intiso D, Pilotto A, Logroscino G, Panza F (2015) Employment of higher doses of botulinum toxin type A to reduce spasticity after stroke. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences* 350(1–2): 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2015.01.033>
- Sławek J, Car H, Bonikowski M, Bogucki A, Koziorowski D, Potulska-Chromik A, Rudzińska M (2010) Czy wszystkie preparaty toksyny botulinowej typu A są takie same? Porównanie trzech preparatów toksyny botulinowej typu A w zarejestrowanych wskazaniach w neurologii [Are botulinum toxin type A preparations really the same medication? A comparison of three botulinum toxin A for variations in labelled neurological indications]. *Neurologia i Neurochirurgia Polska* 44(1): 43–64. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0028-3843\(14\)60406-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0028-3843(14)60406-0)
- Small R (2014) Botulinum toxin injection for facial wrinkles. *American Family Physician* 90(3): 168–175.
- Sugrue CM, Kelly JL, McInerney N (2019) Botulinum Toxin Treatment for Mild to Moderate Platysma Bands: A Systematic Review of Efficacy, Safety, and Injection Technique. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal* 39(2): 201–206. <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjy179>
- Szuch E, Caress JB, Paudyal B, Brashear A, Cartwright MS, Strowd RE III (2017) Head drop after botox: Electrodiagnostic evaluation of iatrogenic botulinum toxicity. *Clinical Neurology and Neurosurgery* 156: 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clineuro.2017.02.012>
- Vittal H, Pasricha PF (2006) Botulinum toxin for gastrointestinal disorders: therapy and mechanisms. *Neurotoxicity Research* 9(2–3): 149–159. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03033934>
- Whitcup SM (2021) The History of Botulinum Toxins in Medicine: A Thousand Year Journey. *Handbook of Experimental Pharmacology* 263: 3–10. https://doi.org/10.1007/164_2019_271
- Winner BM, Bodt SML, McNutt PM (2020) Special Delivery: Potential Mechanisms of Botulinum Neurotoxin Uptake and Trafficking within Motor Nerve Terminals. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 21(22): 8715. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21228715>
- Yamaguchi D, Tsuruoka N, Sakata Y, Shimoda R, Fujimoto K, Iwakiri R (2015) Safety and efficacy of botulinum toxin injection therapy for esophageal achalasia in Japan. *Journal of Clinical Biochemistry and Nutrition* 57(3): 239–243. <https://doi.org/10.3164/jcfn.15-47>
- Yi KH, Lee JH, Seo KK, Kim HJ (2024) Anatomical Proposal for Botulinum Neurotoxin Injection for Horizontal Forehead Lines. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery* 153(2): 322e–325e. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.00000000000010469>
- Yokoyama O, Honda M, Yamanishi T, Sekiguchi Y, Fujii K, Nakayama T, Mogi T (2020) OnabotulinumtoxinA (botulinum toxin type A) for the treatment of Japanese patients with overactive bladder and urinary incontinence: Results of single-dose treatment from a phase III, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial (interim analysis). *International Journal of Urology* 27(3): 227–234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/iju.14176>